

**A new species of the genus *Psalidognathus* Gray, 1831
(Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) from Colombia**

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Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, new species, Colombia.

Abstract: *Psalidognathus victorsinyaevi*, **sp. n.** from Colombia close to *P. rufescens* Quentin & Villiers, 1983 from Ecuador is described.

Introduction

Psalidognathus Gray in Griffith, 1831 is one of the most investigated Cerambycidae genera in South America. It includes now 11 species (Bezark, 2019) distributed from Costa-Rica to Peru. One of the well known species *P. rufescens* Quentin & Villiers, 1983 from Ecuador was recently redescribed on the base of two males from Colombia. Now it is clear that another species is distributed in Colombia. Below it is described as new.

***Psalidognathus victorsinyaevi*, sp. n.**

Figs 1-4

Psalidognathus rufescens, Santos-Silva & Komiya, 2012: 17, part. - Ecuador, Colombia.

Type locality. Colombia, Valle del Cauca, Cerro Tokio, 3°29'07"N, 76°43'26"W, 2000 m.

Description. Only three males available; body dark brown, including head, thorax, abdomen, antennae and legs; elytra light-brown, shining.

Head narrower than prothorax (without spines), densely,

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rugosely punctated, with two short ridges behind eyes with a furrow in between; antennal tubercles moderately exposed with short spines above; temples not exposed, strongly narrowed posteriorly; eyes strongly convex, finely faceted, with small and narrow anterior emargination; approached dorsally, the distance between dorsal lobes about as wide as width of 3rd antennal joint; genae very narrow, about as wide as the base of 1st antennal joint, with acute subfossal processes; mandibulae strongly curved, about as long as head or considerably longer (in holotype), each with three internal dents (anterior is the longest).

Antennae long, surpassing elytral apices with two apical joints; 1st antennal joint coarsely sculptured, nearly attains anterior pronotal margin; 2nd joint very narrow, strongly transverse; 3rd joint about 1.7 (or 2 in holotype) times longer than 1st; 4th joint rather shorter and about equal to 5th; 4th - 10th joints more or less carinated; 3rd - 10th joints with short, but distinct outer apical spines; internal antennal spines could be also distinct, but in holotype nearly obliterated; 11th joint with hardly pronounced appendage.

Palpi very long and narrow, much longer than mandibulae; apical palpal joint slightly dilated distally.

Prothorax transverse, but relatively narrow, about 1.8 (or 2 in holotype) times shorter than basal width; with 3 very long and narrow lateral spines on each side, just a little shorter than 1st antennal joint; pronotum relatively flat, with small, but rough granulation, covered with very dense and long down pubescence; anterior pronotal margin straight, posterior roundly exposed; scutellum narrow, semicircular, covered with very short, dark brown, sparse pubescence; mesothorax and metathorax ventrally densely pubescent;

Elytra about 2.3 time longer than wide, glabrous, nearly parallel sided, strongly carinated, with distinct transverse rugae in holotype; smooth in between carinae; humeral angles with long spines; apical elytral spines short. but distinct.

Legs very long and narrow; anterior tibiae slightly widened near middle and here with a brush of moderately long setae; posterior tarsi about as long as posterior tibiae; 1st tarsal joint a little shorter than 2nd and 3th combined; apical tarsal joint longer than others

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combined; apices of 1st-3rd joints of posterior tarsi with short spines.

Abdomen partly pubescent with long and dense setae.

Body length: 44.0-52.0 mm, width: 15.0-17.0 mm.

Remark. Two males described by Santos-Silva & Komiya (2012) from Colombia definitely belong to our new species, so we could use here the size of both specimens (body length: 52.0-60.9 mm, width: 16.0-18.4 mm), so the body length of the new species: 44.0-60.9 mm, width: 15.0-18.4 mm. Female from Colombia mentioned by Santos-Silva & Komiya (2012) from Valle Cosumbo River was 58.0 mm long.

Differential diagnosis. The species is very close to *P. rufescens* from Ecuador, but differs by longer mandibulae, distinctly less wide prothorax, small scutellum, dark-brown pronotal and elytral pubescence, darker elytra.

Materials. Holotype (fig. 1-2), male, Colombia, Valle del Cauca, Cerro Tokio, 3°29'07"N, 76°43'26"W, 2000 m, 27-29.3.2017, V. Sinyaev leg. - collection of V.Sinyaev, Moscow; paratypes: 2 males with same label - collection of V.Sinyaev, Moscow.

Note. We include in the type series 3 specimens described from Colombia by Santos-Silva & Komiya (2012) as *P. rufescens*, because their descriptions of the males totally fits to our materials. More over both males described by Santos-Silva & Komiya (2012) belongs to the same area (Valle del Cauca) as our holotype, or probably to the same population (Cali). A female mentioned by Santos-Silva & Komiya (2012) from the Lackerbeck collection also originated from Colombia. So, three more paratypes are designated here: male, "COLOMBIA, Valle Del Cauca: male, [no date indicated], L. C. Locarno col. (MZSP)" - Museu de Zoologia, Universidade de São Paulo, São Paulo, Brazil; male, "Cali (1000 m), male, 10.XII.19745 (sic!), Leon Denhez col. (ZKCO)" - Ziro Komiya Collection, Tokyo, Japan; female, "Colombia, Valle Cosumbo River, Pital R., Big River Calima, 900m, IV.-V.1984, R. MARX, in Coll. LACKERBECK".

Etymology. The specie is dedicated to Viktor Sinyaev who collected three males of the type series.

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2 Colombia 27-29.3.2017
Valle del Cauca
Cerro Tokio 2000 m
3°29'07"N, 76°43'26"W
V. Sinyaev leg.

HOLOTYPE
Psalidognathus
VICTORSINYAEVI
M.Lazarev, S.Murzin det. 2019

Figs 1-2. *Psalidognathus victorsinyaevi*, sp. n.: 1 - holotype, male; 2 - labels of the holotype.

Figs 3-4. *Psalidognathus victorsinyaevi*, **sp. n.**: males, paratypes.

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Figs 5-6. *Psalidognathus rufescens* Quentin & Villiers, 1983: 5 - male, holotype; 6 - labels of the holotype. (Foto by <http://www.prioninae.eu>)

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